

EU MISSION 'A SOIL DEAL FOR EUROPE'

Healthy soils are essential to life on Earth. They are the foundation of our food systems, they also provide clean water and habitats for biodiversity while contributing to climate resilience. Yet, between 60% and 70% of soils in the EU are considered unhealthy. While it can take hundreds of years to form just one centimetre of soil, it can be lost in a single rainstorm or through industrial damage.

The EC launched the Mission '**A Soil Deal for Europe**'- Horizon Europe programme -**to create 100 living labs and lighthouses** in rural and urban areas to drive the transition to healthy soils by 2030.

THE MISSION SOIL WILL¹:

- Create knowledge and solutions for soil health,
- Advance the development of a harmonised framework for soil monitoring in Europe,
- Increase people's awareness of the vital importance of soils,
- Support the EU's ambition to lead on global commitments, notably the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and contribute to the European Green Deal targets.*

¹ European Commission

*[more information in the Mission implementation plan.](#)

THE 8 MISSION OBJECTIVES

1

Reduce desertification

2

Conserve soil organic carbon stocks

3

Stop soil sealing & increase re-use of urban soils

4

Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

5

Prevent erosion

6

Improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity

7

Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

8

Improve soil literacy in society

THE MISSION SOIL LIVING LABS ARE...

“user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists, and other relevant partners in systemic research and codesign, testing, monitoring, and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption of best practices.” Factsheet - EU Mission Soil Deal for Europe: Living labs and lighthouses.

By working in diverse environments, such as farms, forests, urban areas, and industrial sites, Living Labs aim to develop tailored solutions that can be replicated and scaled. They also serve as hubs for exchanging best practices, validating methodologies, and promoting sustainable soil management. This approach not only accelerates the adoption of effective practices but also bridges the gap between science and practical implementation.

CHALLENGES IN SOIL-RELATED ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

Soil health underpins essential ecosystem services (SES) such as food production, fresh water supply, habitat for biodiversity, critical to achieving many Sustainable Development Goals. Yet, these services are often overlooked, undervalued, or poorly integrated into decision-making and land management.

A key challenge is **to improve awareness on SES and to map these in a way that is understandable for decision makers, land users, and planners**. It is also important to value them and elaborate how to divide costs and benefits (who invests, who benefits). Bringing knowledge of SES into policy in practice is another challenge. What is the best way to implement SES in land and soil management, spatial planning, and policymaking — including how to capture and consider intangible synergies and trade-offs?

SPECIFIC KEY CHALLENGES

- **Erosion:** The loss of topsoil due to wind and water erosion reduces soil fertility and agricultural productivity.
- **Pollution:** Contamination from industrial waste, pesticides, and heavy metals harms soil organisms and reduces its quality.
- **Organic Matter Loss:** Decreasing levels of organic matter affect soil structure, water retention, and nutrient availability.
- **Salinisation:** Excessive salt accumulation, often due to poor irrigation practices, makes soil less suitable for crops.
- **Compaction:** Heavy machinery and overgrazing compact the soil reducing its ability to absorb water and support plant roots.
- **Climate Stress:** Rising temperature and changing precipitation patterns exacerbate droughts, floods and other stresses on soil.
- **Nutrient Imbalance:** Overuse or underuse of fertilisers disrupts the natural nutrient cycles, leading to deficiencies or toxicities.

These challenges require sustainable practices like conservation tillage, crop rotation, organic farming, and better water management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To protect SES, we need sustainable practices such as **conservation tillage, crop rotation, organic amendments, and smarter water use.**

Equally important is **raising awareness of SES, mapping their benefits clearly,** and incorporating them into **land planning and policy.**

This includes defining who bears the costs, who gains benefits, and understanding trade-offs between different land uses.

THE QUADRUPLE HELIX TYPES OF STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED IN LIVING LABS

An essential feature of Living Labs is their user-centric approach, involving all key actors and end-users throughout the innovation process. While specific participants vary by context, they can be grouped using the **Quadruple Helix Model**—Academia, Industry, Government, and Civil Society—forming a **Public-Private-People Partnership (PPPP)** that enables real co-creation and impact.

This inclusive model supports co-learning and ensures that solutions are not only scientifically sound but also practical, economically viable, socially accepted, and environmentally sustainable.

EXAMPLES OF LIVING LAB STAKEHOLDERS ADDRESSING SOIL-RELATED ECOSYSTEM SERVICES INCLUDE:

Management and improvement of soil health to support ecosystem services for all land uses is important across all the stakeholders involved, each drawing corresponding benefits:

- **GOVERNMENT & PUBLIC SECTOR:** Local, regional and national authorities can benefit from Living Labs focused on SES, where these contribute to societal and sustainability objectives.
- **LAND USERS:** Landowners, nature protection organisations, land developers, and farmers can benefit from the SES by improving soil health, where direct gains improve long-term food, fiber, and wood production, climate adaptation, water purification and other services.
- **ACADEMIA:** Researchers and consultants from environmental, economic and social sciences can be interested in the valuation of SES, their effective implementation in practice and policy, but also in the question as to how best to change habits of land users, practitioners and citizens.
- **CITIZENS, CIVIL SOCIETY & USERS:** Might be users of potential Living Labs that can improve their direct living environment, contribute to their environmental knowledge and connection, and their understanding of local green areas and gardens, biodiversity, and climate adaptation.

WHICH ADDED VALUE CAN CO-CREATION BRING IN THIS FIELD?

To bring knowledge of SES into practice and policy, co-creation between different stakeholders is crucial. This entails shared knowledge about SES, tradeoff synergies, impacts from land use on soil health and the contribution of SES to land use. Triple bottom line (environmental, social, and economic) knowledge is needed to value SES and to implement practical changes in the ways that different land users do their work. This necessitates improvements in the awareness of the wider values SES can provide and enabling experimentation and showcasing as to what works best.

The co-creation approach therefore contributes directly to tackling societal challenges and providing for societal needs to be able to further promote and achieve the restoration of soils and implementation of SES.

WHICH ACTIVITIES CAN MISSION SOIL LIVING LABS PERFORM IN THE FIELD OF SES?

Mission Soil Living Labs can provide stakeholders a focus to test and discuss soil management practices that improve soil health, elaborate soil inclusive planning and adopt nature-positive designs making use of SES for different land uses. An important part of Mission Soil Living Labs featuring SES lies in enhanced soil literacy or awareness about what benefit (i.e. what kind and how much) soils can offer, and how best to avoid soil degradation.

"If you take care of the soil, the soil will take care of you"

**MARGOT DE CLEEN
POLICYMAKER
DUTCH MINISTRY OF INFRASTRUCTURE AND WATER**

CRITERIA TO IDENTIFY

LIVING LABS*

Aims

- **Innovation, co-creation**, formal learning
- Contribution to **societal challenges**
- **Improving soil health and related ecosystem services** (= > mission objectives)

Participants

Public-private people partnership:

- **Real soil managers** (farmers, advisors, foresters, city greens managers, allotment holders, etc.) to be at the centre of the innovation process.
- **Other stakeholders:** Associations and organisations with an interest in soil health, local or regional government, scientists from a variety of fields outside of soil (natural sciences, social and behavioural sciences), and the wider public.

Activities

- **Co-creation, co-development & experimentation** of innovations improving soil health and related ecosystems
- **Research on impact of these innovative practices on ecosystems**
- **Networking** and **knowledge exchange**
- **Demonstration** (in particular lighthouses)

Context

- Multiple **disciplines** (-> transdisciplinary, inc. social sciences), **methods, dimensions** (technical, economic, social)
- **Place-based** approach and **real-life context** = real farms/forest/urban sites
- **Robust scientific setup for ecosystem assessment**
- **Openness**, communication, dissemination

*adapted from McPhee et al. (2021)

LIGHTHOUSES

As lighthouses are sites achieving exemplary performance in terms of soil health improvement, the criteria for selecting them will be based on the **mission objectives**, indicators, and thresholds as defined by the monitoring programme:

- **Demonstration, dissemination, and promotion** to soil managers, the public, and the policy arena, at the landscape scale and beyond, of land-use systems that satisfy criteria for sustainable development, in particular in terms of soil health and related ecosystem services.
- Reaching out to the **policy arena** linking results of the Lighthouses to environmental rules and regulations. This is in line with science-based policy support and governance.

HOW TO PARTICIPATE? TWO LIVING LAB TOPICS

1) Brownfield

HORIZON-MISS-2025-05-SOIL-01: Living Labs for soil remediation and green redevelopment of **brownfields**

- **Single-stage** submission
- **Deadline:** 30 September 2025
- 4-5 Living Labs for each application - should be located in at least three different Member States and/or Associated Countries

2) Biogeographical regions

HORIZON-MISS-2025-05-SOIL-01-two-stage: Living labs to enhance soil health in **Continental, Boreal and Alpine biogeographical regions**

- **Two-stage** submission (First, applicants submit a brief outline. Selected proposals are then invited to submit a full application)
- **Deadline:** 4 September 2025 (first stage) and 18 February 2026 (second stage).
- 4-5 Living Labs for each application - **Most of the living labs** (i.e., 3 out of 4, or 4 out of 5) must be located **within the chosen region**

Research and Innovation Actions:

100% funding for any actor
Proposals must apply the multi-actor approach
Support to third parties is allowed

WANT TO EXPLORE FURTHER?

Biogeographical Regions factsheet

Both Living Lab topics on the SOILL website

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SOILL HUB

A collaborative space dedicated to soil health.

HELPDESK

A wide network of experts ready to provide guidance and answers on many topics.